

GEOECOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF SPECIALLY PROTECTED AREAS OF KASHKADARYA NATURAL GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRICT

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Abstract: *This article deals with the lifestyles of people with disabilities, the power that encourage disable people to achieve goals. Furthermore, information about famous people who obtained success in their life were given.*

Key Words: *"river lost in the sand", abundance, flora and fauna, horizontal, elevation zonal, precipitation, agro-ecosystems, anthropogenic landscapes.*

Geographic position of Uzbekistan, diversity of physiographic conditions determine its rich biological diversity. Vast deserts of Uzbekistan, mountain steppes, forests, alpine meadows, and waterbodies are all characteristic ecosystems with typical ecological and faunistic systems. Remaining natural ecosystems of Uzbekistan help to stabilize the territories, in which the lands have lost their ability to support sustainable favorable environment due to the disturbance caused by human activities. Kashkadarya Region, is one of the [regions of Uzbekistan](#), located in the south-eastern part of the country in the basin of the river Kashkadarya and on the western slopes of the [Pamir-Alay](#) mountains. It borders with [Tajikistan](#), [Turkmenistan](#), [Samarqand](#) [Region](#), [Bukhara Region](#) and [Surxondaryo Region](#). It covers an area of 28,570 km². The population is estimated 3,408,345 (2022), with 57% living in rural areas. The regional capital is [Qarshi](#).

Kashkadarya region is one of the most environmentally friendly, located in the basin of the Kashkadarya river. The toponym Kashkadarya has several meanings: "river lost in the sand" and "transparent, clean river". The administrative center of the region is the city of Karshi, which celebrated its 2700th anniversary in 2006. Due to the continental climate (sometimes even subtropical) on the slope of the Pamir-Alai mountains, the air in the region is the purest, and the natural landscape fascinates with its flora and fauna. There are several well – known nature reserves in the region

- Kitab, Gissar and Kizil-say nature reserve. It is here in the foothills that the colorful jewels of nature are grown-pomegranates, quinces, peaches, pears, cherries, lemons. Huge abundance of vegetables, several types of nuts: pistachios, peanuts, walnuts. Spacious pastures allow you to raise livestock. And all this under the warm sun, among wide fields and ancient mounds.

In addition to the excellent ecology and beautiful nature, the region is rich in ancient cities and architectural monuments. The birthplace of the outstanding commander Amir Timur - the city of Shakhrisabz in Kashkadarya region is listed as a UNESCO World Cultural heritage. The region is located in the Kashkadarya river basin, on the western slope of the Pamir-Alai mountains. The Kashkadarya region has significant petroleum and natural gas reserves. Major agricultural activities include cotton, various crops and livestock. The irrigation infrastructure is very well developed with the large Tollimarjon reservoir providing reliable water source. The share of agricultural production in Kashkadarya in the gross regional product is more than 40%. Kashkadarya is one of the main sources of grain, cotton and other agricultural products in Uzbekistan producing 10.2% of all agricultural products, 98% of gas, and more than 80% of oil extracted of the country's total.

The formation of anthropogenic landscapes and population distribution in the Kashkadaryaregion are inextricably linked. According to the conducted researches, it can be seen that the most densely populated anthropogenic landscapes are located in Shahrissabz, Yakkabog, Kitab districts, located in the middle high mountains and foothills. The population of Kashkadarya region is growing from year to year, as can be seen in Figure 1. The population of the province has increased by 600,000 in 10 years, but the level of urbanization is low. This is due to the improvement of socio-economic conditions and well-being in rural areas, as well as high birth rates in rural areas. The Kashkadarya Basin, located in the center of the southern part of Central Asia, has a mountain-plain relief, and the horizontal and elevation zonal features of landscapes ride on heat and humidity conditions, population characteristics, relief, and man-made lands and other factors. Landscapes of the Kashkadarya oasis have long been used in human economic activity. Therefore, in a large part of the oasis, especially in its plains, the landscapes have undergone various anthropogenic changes, and the role of anthropogenic factors in their description must be taken into account. The Kashkadarya oasis has a number of favorable climatic conditions for agricultural production. The

geographical location of the Kashkadarya oasis and its surface structure play an important role in the composition of the agro-climate of this region.

Experts from Central Asian agroclimatic science L.N. Babushkin and N.A. The Kogays divide the plain part of the Kashkadarya basin into three agro-climatic regions: Lower Kashkadarya, Guzar and Shakhrisabz [3]. As Kashkadarya region is located in both plain and mountainous areas, the group of plain and mountainous agro-climatic regions is separated individually. Underlying this separation is the factor of regional variation of humidity and heat in the plains, and the reason for the distribution of climatic elements in the mountains on the basis of the law of altitude zoning. In the Kashkadarya oasis, the region's agriculture has been developing in the traditional way since ancient times. Therefore, the largest area in the oasis is occupied by agricultural landscapes – agro-landscapes associated with anthropogenic activities. Analysis of the land fund of Kashkadarya region and structural changes in its composition, identification of their main and priority directions play an important role in the effective use of agro-landscapes and the organization of cultural landscapes. Kashkadarya region is one of the largest regions of Uzbekistan in terms of land area, with a total land area of 2,856.8 thousand hectares. According to the Statistics Department of Kashkadarya region, as of January 2020, there are 2143.3 thousand hectares of agricultural land in the region, including 109.1 thousand hectares of forests, 35.7 thousand hectares of gardens and vineyards. There are 417.2 thousand hectares of irrigated lands and 253.2 thousand hectares of dry lands. Dry lands are areas where the average annual rainfall exceeds 250 mm, and the cultivation of agricultural crops is carried out only at the expense of precipitation. The existing land resources of the Kashkadarya oasis allow for large-scale use in arable farming. In Kashkadarya region, the area of arable land is 670.5 thousand hectares or about 23.7% of the total area, of which 253.2 thousand hectares or 9.1% of the total arable land is used for non-irrigated farming.

Considering all facts above we should conclude that the natural complex of any place is the basis of rational use of ecological-geographical system with its own order of development, individual features, rational use of available lands in Kashkadarya oasis is of great importance for further development of agriculture and soil fertility. It should be noted that agrolandscapes acquire new social qualities in addition to their natural qualities. It is precisely because of the existence of unique development that only complexes that obey natural laws create

anthropogenic landscapes. A map of agro-landscapes and landscape salinity of Kashkadarya region on a scale of 1: 300,000 was created. The above data allow identifying, forecasting the development of negative processes in the agro-landscapes of the Kashkadarya oasis and, if necessary, adapting them to the creation of more extensive and environmentally sustainable agro-ecosystems which is important in obtaining high yields of agricultural crops and forecasting the amount of yield in our country.

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